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Optical Spring Limitations in Phonon Lasing

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To my cat Pejxu

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Abstract

This report provides a comprehensive review of optomechanical systems and cavity physics, with a focus on the effects of the optical spring effect, particularly in multimode phonon lasing. In contrast with single-mode coupling in traditional optomechanical cavities, this research explores how the optical spring effect has a comparatively smaller impact in systems with multiple mechanical modes. This is especially relevant when these systems achieve a mode-locked state through techniques like Floquet dynamics. Experimental and theoretical investigations suggest that multimode phonon lasing can lead to significantly improved long-term frequency stability when compared to single-mode operation. This analysis delves into the conditions under which the frequency shifts induced by the optical spring effect remain smaller than the mechanical linewidths, specifically considering three modes in the multimode system, ensuring robust mode locking and stable operation. This work paves the way for future exploration into increasing the mode count for multimode systems to potentially achieve even stronger effects and enhance the functionalities of these systems.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Background & Literature Overview	3
2.1	Hamiltonian description of Optomechanics	3
2.2	Linearised Optomechanical dynamics	13
2.3	Phonon Dynamics	16
2.4	Cavity Optomechanics	18
2.5	Optical Spring Effect	21
3	Optical Spring Effect in Multimode Optomechanical system	31
3.1	Results	34
3.2	Discussion	35
4	Conclusion	39
	References	41

List of Figures

2.1	Photon-phonon Scattering process in blue and red detuning taken from [5].	17
2.2	A simple Fabry-Pérot setup, consisting of a laser driving the optical cavity where the light interacts with the-end mirror as a result of the radiation pressure, resulting in the mechanical oscillator vibrating taken from [6].	19
2.3	A plot of the scaled optomechanical damping rate as a function of the detuning. Positive peaks denote stronger damping, meanwhile negative peaks indicate an anti-damping.	27
2.4	Frequency shift based on the optomechanical interaction as a function of the detuning.	28
3.1	A schematic of three mechanical modes coupled to one optical mode.	31
3.2	The frequency shift for one Ω_M with different κ values in the resolved sideband regime $\kappa/\Omega_M < 1$ (solid line) and in the unresolved sideband regime $\kappa/\Omega_M > 1$ (dashed line).	37

List of Tables

3.1	Experimental values.	34
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Introduction

The ability to control mechanical motion using light at the nanoscale offers insight into new regimes of physics, where precision motivates the pursuit of stable phonon lasing in optomechanical systems which is crucial in applications requiring high coherence and precision measurements, such as signal generation and precision sensing. Moreover, the study of multimode lasing dynamics provides a deeper insight into non-linear phenomena and mode selection mechanisms, contributing to a deeper understanding of cavity optomechanics. We start off by introducing the fundamental concepts of cavity optomechanics, focusing on the coherent control of mechanical resonators and the quantum nature of radiation pressure. In Chapter 2, we begin by exploring the interaction between light and mechanics at the nanoscale through radiation pressure in optical cavities, which forms the basis for optomechanics. This chapter covers the Hamiltonian description of the optomechanical interaction. We then discuss the optical spring effect, a fundamental consequence from the interaction between light and matter, and its implications. In Chapter 3, we extend the analysis to a multimode optomechanical system with three mechanical modes. We explore the optical spring effect's limitations in phonon lasing, focusing on how frequency shifts induced by the optical spring affect the stability of mode-locked coherent oscillations. Using existing experimental parameters, we calculate the frequency shifts and compare them to the mechanical linewidth to assess their impact on lasing conditions. Our aim is to achieve stable, self-oscillations for phonon lasing using a modulated optical drive in the unresolved regime. We aim to first develop a theoretical model for a driven multimode system, analyse and identify the lasing conditions for the modes, examine the implications of the optical spring effect and contain it for coherent and stable mechanical oscillations. Finally, we conclude with a discussion of our findings in the conclusion.

Background & Literature Overview

We start off by exploring light and mechanics and their interaction which is the basis for optomechanics. This area involves quantum optics, solid state physics and nanophysics and has seen significant advancements in recent years, having taken the interest of physicists since the late 20th and early 21st centuries.

The core idea is that light can be used to manipulate and detect the motion of mechanical systems, and conversely, using mechanical motion to control light. Various experimental setups have been developed such as laser-driven optical cavities with moving mirrors [1], nanobeams or vibrating plate capacitors in superconducting microwave resonators [2], photonic crystals patterned into free-standing nanobeams [3, 4].

2.1 | Hamiltonian description of Optomechanics

Firstly, we explore the quantisation of the electromagnetic field since optomechanics involves the interaction between light and mechanical systems. We start by using source free Maxwell's equations since the free electromagnetic field obeys it as we are considering current and charge free systems.

Taking the notations for the permeability and electric permittivity of free space, respectively, μ_0, ϵ_0 .

We know that Maxwell's equations are invariant under certain potential transformations. This holds when there are no sources (currents or charges) present. Using the Coulomb gauge to write Maxwell's equations in terms of the vector potential \mathbf{A} . The Coulomb gauge simplifies the process mathematically by ensuring $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0$, which eliminates redundant degrees of freedom.

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A},$$

$$\mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t},$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0.$$

We set \mathbf{A} to be

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A},$$

which implies that

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}).$$

Now, using the vector identity for a curl of curl,

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{\mu_0} [\nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} - \nabla^2 \mathbf{A})], \\ &= -\frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla^2 \mathbf{A}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\mathbf{D} = \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}$, then we get $\frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} = -\epsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}}{\partial t^2}$ Therefore,

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}}{\partial t^2}. \quad (2.1)$$

Given that $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\mu_0 \epsilon_0}}$.

Eq. (2.1) gives us the wave equation for the vector potential. This potential must be real and harmonic. We can separate the vector potential into two complex terms

$$\mathbf{A}(r, t) = \mathbf{A}^{(+)}(r, t) + \mathbf{A}^{(-)}(r, t)$$

where $A^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ represents all the amplitudes that oscillate as $e^{-i\omega t}$ for $\omega > 0$, while $A^{(-)}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ represents those that oscillate as $e^{i\omega t}$.

Here, $\mathbf{A}^{(+)}$ and $\mathbf{A}^{(-)}$ are complex functions. To ensure that $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ remains real, these complex terms must satisfy the condition

$$\mathbf{A}^{(-)}(\mathbf{r}, t) = [\mathbf{A}^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)]^*.$$

Since the wave equation is linear, the sum of solutions is also a solution. To analyse the spatial behaviour, we expand $\mathbf{A}^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ as a sum over modes \mathbf{k}

$$\mathbf{A}^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t}. \quad (2.2)$$

where $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$ is the angular frequency of mode \mathbf{k} , ϵ_0 is the medium permittivity, $a_{\mathbf{k}}$ is the complex amplitude for mode \mathbf{k} and $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$ is the spatial mode function which represents spatial variations of the electromagnetic field and are eigenfunctions of the Laplacian operator which are solutions to the wave equation.

The normalization factor $\sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}}$ ensures that each mode has energy levels consistent with quantum harmonic oscillators (this reflects the quantized nature of electromagnetic waves, where the energy of each mode is an integer multiple of $\hbar\omega$), where the energy E_n is given by $E_n = \hbar\omega_{\mathbf{k}} (n + \frac{1}{2})$.

This is important for maintaining energy quantization in the system. It also guarantees that the vector potential \mathbf{A} has the correct physical dimensions. Additionally, it also allows for proper quantization by ensuring that the canonical commutation relations, $[a_{\mathbf{k}}, a_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger] = \delta_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}'}$, are satisfied, which ensures the bosonic nature of the field. It also secures the orthogonality of different modes, such that modes \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{k}' do not interfere with each other. Finally, the normalization term correctly scales the mode amplitudes $a_{\mathbf{k}}$, so that they are proportional to fundamental constants like \hbar , $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$, and ϵ_0 , making the expression physically meaningful.

In the study of electromagnetic fields, especially when confined in a volume of space - this enforces modes to countable terms, it is better to represent the vector potential using a discrete set of orthogonal mode functions rather than a continuous spectrum, reducing the problem to a finite number of modes.

In quantum electrodynamics, the vector potential is often expanded in terms of discrete orthogonal mode functions within a finite volume. This expansion facilitates the quantization of the electromagnetic field by expressing it as a sum over independent modes. In this derivation, we start from the mode expansion of the positive-frequency component of the vector potential and derive the corresponding equation involving its second time derivative. We begin with the positive-frequency component of the vector potential $A^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, which is expressed as a sum over discrete orthogonal mode functions

The first temporal derivative is given as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t}) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) (-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t}.$$

and we find the second temporal derivative

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{A}^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t^2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}^{(+)}(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} \right) \\
 &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}} e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} \right) \\
 &= \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) (-\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

Where the spacial derivatives satisfy

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{A}^{(+)} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} [\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})] e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t}. \tag{2.4}$$

For all values of k ,

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) (-\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} a_{\mathbf{k}} [\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})] e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t}.$$

This requires the mode functions will fulfil the following equation

$$\left(\nabla^2 + \frac{\omega_{\mathbf{k}}^2}{c^2} \right) \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = 0. \tag{2.5}$$

The vector mode functions $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r})$, corresponding to the frequencies $\omega_{\mathbf{k}}$, must satisfy the wave equation under the assumption that the volume is free from any refractive materials.

Additionally, the mode functions must adhere to the transversality condition

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = 0. \tag{2.6}$$

This indicates that the vector potential \mathbf{A} associated with these modes is transverse to the direction of propagation. These conditions insure that the waves remain divergence free and transverse. Now we quantize in terms of fock States, or number States.

When quantizing the electromagnetic field, the mode amplitudes $a_{\mathbf{k}}$ and their Hermitian conjugates $a_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger$ are promoted to operators that describe the photons, act on the Hilbert space of the quantized field. These annihilation and creation operators, obey the following commutation relations

$$[a_{\mathbf{k}}, a_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger] = \delta_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'}, \quad [a_{\mathbf{k}}, a_{\mathbf{k}'}] = 0, \quad [a_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger, a_{\mathbf{k}'}^\dagger] = 0.$$

These relations are important for defining the quantized electromagnetic field in terms of fock states . Each Fock state $|n_{\mathbf{k}}\rangle$ represents a state with a well-defined number $n_{\mathbf{k}}$ of photons in mode \mathbf{k} .

We can now express the vector potential $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ in terms of the creation and annihilation operators

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\omega_{\mathbf{k}}\epsilon_0}} \left(a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} + a_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} \right). \quad (2.7)$$

This sum represents all the modes allowed by the current situation. Where $k = (\mathbf{k}, \lambda)$. This defines each mode by both its propagation direction \mathbf{k} and its polarization. The corresponding electric field form

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) = i \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar\omega_{\mathbf{k}}}{2\epsilon_0}} \left[a_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) e^{-i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} - a_{\mathbf{k}}^\dagger \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\omega_{\mathbf{k}}t} \right]. \quad (2.8)$$

Keeping the transversality and orthonormality of the mode functions, where the mode functions $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}$ are normalized as

$$\int_V \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}}^*(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{k}'}(\mathbf{r}) d^3r = \delta_{\mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'}$$

This orthonormality ensures that different modes \mathbf{k} and \mathbf{k}' remain independent. The classical Hamiltonian for the electromagnetic field is given by

$$\hat{H} = \frac{1}{2} \int (\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}^2 + \mu_0 \mathbf{H}^2) d\mathbf{r}$$

We start by defining the electric and magnetic fields in terms of the vector potential $\hat{\mathbf{A}}$

$$\hat{\mathbf{E}} = -\frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{A}}}{\partial t}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{H}} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \nabla \times \hat{\mathbf{A}}.$$

To proceed, consider the integral

$$\int_V (\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \mathbf{u}_k d\mathbf{r}.$$

Using the vector identity $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_k) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_k$ and the fact that $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}_k = 0$, this reduces to

$$\int_V (\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \mathbf{u}_k d\mathbf{r} = - \int_V (\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \mathbf{u}_k d\mathbf{r}.$$

Next, we apply the divergence theorem to convert the volume integral to a surface integral

$$\int_V (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) d\mathbf{r} = \int_S (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \mathbf{u}_k d\mathbf{s} - \int_V (\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \mathbf{u}_k d\mathbf{r}.$$

Assuming boundary conditions that make the surface term vanish, we are left with

$$\int_V (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) d\mathbf{r} = - \int_V (\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot \mathbf{u}_k d\mathbf{r}.$$

From the wave equation in free space, each mode \mathbf{u}_k must satisfy

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{u}_k = - \frac{\omega_k^2}{c^2} \mathbf{u}_k.$$

Continuing, now we can expand to

$$\int (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) d\mathbf{r} = \frac{\omega_k^2}{c^2} \int \mathbf{u}_k \cdot \mathbf{u}'_k d\mathbf{r}.$$

We know that $\hat{\mathbf{E}}$ is Eq. (2.8). This allows us to calculate the energy density of the quantized electromagnetic field $\epsilon_0 \hat{\mathbf{E}}^2$. Working it out gives

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_0 \hat{\mathbf{E}}^2 = & \sum_{k,k'} \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\omega_k \omega_{k'}} \left[\hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'} (\mathbf{u}_k \cdot \mathbf{u}_{k'}) e^{-i(\omega_k + \omega_{k'})t} \right. \\ & + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger (\mathbf{u}_k^* \cdot \mathbf{u}_{k'}^*) e^{i(\omega_k + \omega_{k'})t} \\ & + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'} (\mathbf{u}_k^* \cdot \mathbf{u}_{k'}) e^{i(\omega_k - \omega_{k'})t} \\ & \left. + \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger (\mathbf{u}_k \cdot \mathbf{u}_{k'}^*) e^{-i(\omega_k - \omega_{k'})t} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\int \mathbf{u}_k^* \cdot \mathbf{u}'_k d\mathbf{r} = \delta_{k,k'}$$

$$\int \mathbf{u}_k \cdot \mathbf{u}_k'^* d\mathbf{r} = \delta_{k,k'}$$

Changing the wave vector, not the polarisation gives $\mathbf{u}_k^* \rightarrow \mathbf{u}_{-k}$ so that $-k = (-\mathbf{k}, \lambda)$ and

$$\int \mathbf{u}_k \cdot \mathbf{u}'_k d\mathbf{r} = \int \mathbf{u}_{-k} \cdot \mathbf{u}'_k d\mathbf{r} = \delta_{k,-k'}.$$

So that we reduce $\epsilon_0 \hat{\mathbf{E}}^2$, and simplify to a single sum, replacing every k' with $-k$

$$\epsilon_0 \hat{\mathbf{E}}^2 = \sum_k \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\omega_k \omega_k} \left[- \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{-k} e^{-i(\omega_k + \omega_k)t} + \dots \right].$$

Provided that $\omega_k^2 = |k|^2$. This simplifies to

$$= \sum_k \frac{\hbar}{2} \sqrt{\omega_k} \left[- \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{-k} e^{-2i\omega_k t} - \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{-k}^\dagger e^{-2i\omega_k t} + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{-k} + \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{-k}^\dagger \right].$$

Such that

$$\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \sum \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\epsilon_0 \omega_k}} \left[\hat{a}_k (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) e^{-i\omega_k t} - \hat{a}_k^\dagger (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k^\dagger) e^{i\omega_k t} \right]$$

$$\mu_0 \hat{\mathbf{H}}^2 = \sum_{k,k'} \frac{\hbar}{2\mu_0 \epsilon_0} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_k \omega_{k'}}} \left[\hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{k'} \left((\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k) \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_{k'}) \right) e^{-i(\omega_k + \omega_{k'})t} \right. \\ \left. + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{k'}^\dagger \left((\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_k^*) \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{u}_{k'}^*) \right) e^{i(\omega_k + \omega_{k'})t} + \dots \right]$$

Integrating this, $\frac{\omega_k^2}{c^2} \delta_{k,k'}$ becomes 1 due to a single sum

$$\sum_k \frac{\hbar}{2} \omega_k \left(\hat{a}_k \hat{a}_{-k} e^{-2i\omega_k t} + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_{-k}^\dagger e^{2i\omega_k t} + \hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k + \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \right).$$

Taking $\int \mu_0 \hat{\mathbf{H}}^2 d\mathbf{r} = \int \epsilon_0 \hat{\mathbf{E}}^2 \mathbf{r}$, expanding this will cancel many terms and result in

$$\hat{H} = \sum_k \frac{\hbar}{2} \omega_k \left(\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k + \hat{a}_k \hat{a}_k^\dagger \right)$$

where $[\hat{a}_k, \hat{a}_k^\dagger] = \mathbb{1}$. So now we can write \hat{H} as

$$\hat{H} = \sum_k \hbar \omega_k \left(\hat{a}_k^\dagger \hat{a}_k + \frac{\mathbb{1}}{2} \right). \quad (2.9)$$

This is the Hamiltonian for a collection of independent quantum harmonic oscillators which form the basis for characterising the uncoupled components of an optomechanical system.

The sum over k shows that the system can consist of many different bosonic modes, each with its own frequency.

This form of the Hamiltonian represents the sum of the photon number in each mode multiplied by the energy of a photon in that mode, $\hbar \omega_k$, plus a zero-point energy term $\frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ representing the energy of vacuum fluctuations in each mode.

We can identify specific modes in the context of optomechanical cavities. The optical mode of the cavity typically corresponds to one of the indices k of the sum with its respective frequency ω_{cav} where the subscript k is dropped for simplicity when only considering one mode, so ω_{cav} is the resonance frequency at $x = 0$, x being the mechanical displacement.

The Hamiltonian for this uncoupled optical mode is

$$\hbar \omega_{cav} \left(\hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \quad (2.10)$$

where many times the zero-point energy, or the ground-state energy is omitted for simplicity.

Similarly, the mechanical oscillator is taken as another quantum harmonic oscillator, using a different index in the sum or set of indices for multiple modes. In this case the resonance frequency is Ω_m and operators \hat{b} and \hat{b}^\dagger . Its uncoupled Hamiltonian is

$$\hbar\Omega_m \left(\hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b} + \frac{1}{2} \right). \quad (2.11)$$

When we move to the coupled Hamiltonian, we are selecting the specific optical and mechanical modes that are interacting in the system, from the more general Hamiltonian. In this case, the indices k that do not correspond to these interacting modes are taken to be environmental factors for simplified models.

We now move a coupled Hamiltonian where this takes these individual harmonic oscillator Hamiltonians as its foundation and the interaction term that describes how the optical and mechanical modes influence each other is added.

To describe this mathematically, we start off by combining both Hamiltonians of the optical and mechanical modes. So, the Hamiltonian for these uncoupled modes is given by

$$\hat{H}_0 = \hbar\omega_{cav}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} + \hbar\Omega_m\hat{b}^\dagger\hat{b}. \quad (2.12)$$

Since we are considering a cavity, we have to account for its length and any change of it that can occur from the momentum transfer from the reflected photons inside the cavity. Let us take L as the length of the cavity while still considering zero mechanical displacement, we get

$$\omega(\hat{x}) = \omega_{cav} \left(1 - \frac{\hat{x}}{L} + \dots \right) \quad (2.13)$$

where we can observe a term $-\hat{F}\hat{x}$ which represents a fundamental relationship between the force and potential energy in both classical and quantum mechanics. This term is taken to be the force attained by the radiation pressure, defining it as

$$\hat{F} = \frac{\hbar\omega_{cav}}{L}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}. \quad (2.14)$$

We can now explore the interaction of the two modes. This arises from the dependence of the cavity resonance frequency on the displacement \hat{x} of the mechanical oscillator.

This dependence can be approximated as a linear relationship for small displacements,

$$\omega_{cav}(\hat{x}) \approx \omega_{cav} - G\hat{x} \quad (2.15)$$

where G is the optomechanical coupling frequency shift per unit displacement, written as

$$G = -\frac{\partial\omega_{cav}}{\partial\hat{x}}. \quad (2.16)$$

The displacement operator \hat{x} of the mechanical oscillator can be expressed in terms of the zero-point fluctuation amplitude and its annihilation and creation operators, denoted as

$$\hat{x} = x_{ZPF}(\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger). \quad (2.17)$$

The mechanical displacement now determines the Hamiltonian for the optical mode

$$\hat{H}_{opt}(\hat{x}) = \hbar\omega_{cav}(\hat{x})\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} = \hbar(\omega_{cav} - G\hat{x})\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}. \quad (2.18)$$

Substituting for \hat{x} we get

$$\hat{H}_{opt} = \hbar\omega_{cav}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} - \hbar Gx_{ZPF}(\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger)\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}. \quad (2.19)$$

The vacuum optomechanical coupling strength, or the single-photon optomechanical coupling strength, is $g_0 = Gx_{ZPF}$

This single-photon optomechanical coupling strength is correlated with the shift in cavity resonance frequency brought about by the displacement of the mechanical oscillator by one zero-point motion. Thus, the interaction Hamiltonian is

$$\hat{H}_{int} = -\hbar g_0(\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger)\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}. \quad (2.20)$$

This term represents a three-wave mixing process which means that there is the interaction of three quanta: two aspects of the optical field, related to the photon number (these can be the drive field at a certain frequency and the scattered light field at sideband frequency- shifted by the mechanical frequency) and one aspect of the mechanical field, related to the oscillator's displacement [5].

Additionally, this is a type of interaction where the parameters of one system are influenced by a state of another system. This type of coupling that is not simply just an additive or subtractive effect, but rather the mechanical motion influences how the optical system behaves [6]. To describe this explicitly, we have an optical cavity with some specific resonant frequencies at which the light can be strongly enhanced. Taking a mechanical component, such as an end mirror, nanobeam or membrane, this mechanical component undergoes some displacement from its equilibrium position. This movement changes the optical path length, which is the effective distance that light travels through an optical system, in this case the cavity. Thus, this change causes a shift in the resonance frequency of the cavity [6, 7].

The cavity is typically illuminated by a laser at a specific frequency, making the resonance 'driven'. The interplay between the shifted cavity resonance and the driving frequency leads to the observable effects. This type of coupling is a very common situation

for optomechanical interactions- its a 'straightforward' way of obtaining this interaction.

Therefore, the full Hamiltonian, which is the sum of the uncoupled Hamiltonians and the interaction Hamiltonian is written as

$$\hat{H} = \hbar\omega_{cav}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} + \hbar\Omega_M\hat{b}^\dagger\hat{b} - \hbar g_0(\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger)\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}. \quad (2.21)$$

This is the fundamental Hamiltonian that describes the fundamental interaction between the optical field in the cavity and the mechanical oscillator.

To simplify calculations, we move to a frame rotating at the laser frequency which introduces detuning. As mentioned previously, the cavity is driven by a laser at frequency ω_L which is typical in experimental setups. Expanding further, detuning is defined as

$$\Delta = \omega_L - \omega_{cav} \quad (2.22)$$

where detuning Δ can be split into three categories [5]:

- Red detuning (cooling) $\Delta < 0$ or $\omega_L < \omega_{cav}$. This is when the laser frequency is lower than the cavity resonance frequency.
- Blue detuning (heating) $\Delta > 0$ or $\omega_L > \omega_{cav}$. Here the laser frequency is higher than the cavity resonance frequency.
- Resonance $\Delta = 0$ or $\omega_L = \omega_{cav}$. The laser frequency is exactly matched to the cavity resonance frequency.

Detuning can alter the optomechanical interaction leading to several phenomena like the Optical spring effect, damping, types of stability in the laser and squeezing which are just a few properties that can result from this effect.

To implement the laser detuning into the Hamiltonian, we need to move to a frame rotating at the laser frequency ω_L . To do this, we apply a unitary transformation

$$\hat{U}(t) = \exp(i\omega_L\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}t). \quad (2.23)$$

The new Hamiltonian in the rotating frame, \hat{H} , is given by

$$\hat{H}_{rot} = \hat{U}^\dagger(t)\hat{H}_{lab}\hat{U}(t) - i\hbar\hat{U}^\dagger(t)\frac{\partial\hat{U}(t)}{\partial t} \quad (2.24)$$

where this equation represents the transformation of the Hamiltonian of a quantum system from one frame of reference. The time-independent Hamiltonian in this rotating frame, \hat{H}' , is given by

$$\hat{H}' = \hat{U}^\dagger \hat{H} \hat{U} - i\hbar \hat{U}^\dagger \frac{\partial \hat{U}}{\partial t}. \quad (2.25)$$

We now calculate this Hamiltonian for the rotating frame by substituting the terms

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}' &= \exp(-i\omega_L \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} t) \left(\hbar\omega_{\text{cav}} \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + \hbar\Omega_m \hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \hbar g_0 (\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger) \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} \right) \exp(i\omega_L \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} t) \\ &\quad - i\hbar \left(\exp(-i\omega_L \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} t) \frac{\partial \hat{U}}{\partial t} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

Provided that $\frac{\partial \hat{U}}{\partial t} = (i\omega_L \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}) \exp(i\omega_L \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} t)$ and $\hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}$ commutes with any function of itself, including \hat{U} , we obtain the full Hamiltonian in the rotating frame,

$$\hat{H}' = \hbar(\omega_{\text{cav}} - \omega_L) \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + \hbar\Omega_M \hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b} - \hbar g_0 (\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger) \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}. \quad (2.27)$$

Referring back to our definition of detuning in Eq. (2.22), we substitute it into our full Hamiltonian, where it is rotating at the laser frequency

$$\hat{H}' = -\hbar\Delta \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + \hbar\Omega_M \hat{b}^\dagger \hat{b} - \hbar g_0 (\hat{b} + \hat{b}^\dagger) \hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a}. \quad (2.28)$$

In many analyses, the laser driving term is treated separately when deriving the equations of motion using the quantum Langevin equation approach. The Hamiltonian often refers to the non-driven part in the rotating frame.

2.2 | Linearised Optomechanical dynamics

The fundamental equations of motion in optomechanics, are inherently non-linear due to the radiation pressure force being proportional to the squared magnitude of the cavity field amplitude. These equations of motion are

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x}(t) &= -\Omega_M^2 (x(t) - x_0) - \Gamma_M \dot{x}(t) + \frac{(F_{\text{rad}} + F_{\text{ext}}(t))}{m_{\text{eff}}} \\ \dot{\alpha}(t) &= [i(\Delta + Gx(t)) - \kappa/2] \alpha(t) + \sqrt{\kappa_{\text{ex}}} \alpha_{\text{in}}. \end{aligned}$$

Linearising these equations simplifies them into a set of linear differential equations [8]. Even when considering quantum effects, we consider the linearised Hamiltonian, particularly in the weak coupling regime and these result in the linearised quantum

Langevin equations [5]. Linearisation is usually done around a steady-state solution of the system, which is a valid approximation when taking small deviations from this equilibrium. In realistic scenarios, the system operates close to a steady state with small fluctuations.

To obtain the linearized equations of motion, we start by assuming the system is driven by a continuous-wave laser such that α_{in} is constant. In the steady state, the variables $x(t)$ and $\alpha(t)$ will have constant average values, denoted by \bar{x} and $\bar{\alpha}$, respectively.

Setting the time derivatives to zero, we get the steady-state equations

$$0 = -\Omega_M^2(\bar{x} - x_0) + \frac{\hbar G |\bar{\alpha}|^2 + \bar{F}_{ext}}{m_{eff}} \quad (2.29)$$

and

$$0 = [i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2]\bar{\alpha} + \sqrt{\kappa_{ex}}\alpha_{in} \quad (2.30)$$

where we know $F_{rad} = \hbar G |\bar{\alpha}|^2 = (\hbar\omega_{cav}/L)|\bar{\alpha}|^2$ in Eq. (2.29). We take G to encapsulate the dependence for simplicity. G is also equal to g_0/x_{ZPF} . This means that the force exerted by the photons in the cavity per unit length is directly proportional to the ratio of the single-photon coupling strength to the zero-point fluctuation amplitude. From Eq. (2.30), we can find $\bar{\alpha}$ in terms of \bar{x} and the driving laser

$$\bar{\alpha} = \frac{-\sqrt{\kappa_{ex}}\alpha_{in}}{i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2}. \quad (2.31)$$

The steady-state displacement \bar{x} can then be found by substituting $|\bar{\alpha}|^2$ into the first steady-state equation. Now, we introduce small perturbations by considering small deviations around the steady state

$$x(t) = \bar{x} + \delta x(t) \quad (2.32)$$

and

$$\alpha(t) = \bar{\alpha} + \delta\alpha(t). \quad (2.33)$$

Substituting into the original equations of motion and keeping only terms that are linear in the small perturbations δx and $\delta\alpha$.

For the mechanical oscillator

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\ddot{x}(t) &= -\Omega_M^2(\bar{x} + \delta x(t) - x_0) - \Gamma_M(\bar{x} + \delta\dot{x}(t)) + \frac{\hbar G|\bar{\alpha} + \delta\alpha(t)|^2 + \bar{F}_{ext} + \delta F_{ext}(t)}{m_{eff}} \\
&\approx -\Omega_M^2(\bar{x} - x_0) - \Omega_M^2\delta x(t) - \Gamma_M\delta\dot{x}(t) + \frac{\hbar G(\bar{\alpha}\bar{\alpha}^* + \bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^* + \bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha) + \bar{F}_{ext} + \delta F_{ext}(t)}{m_{eff}} \\
&= \underbrace{-\Omega_M^2(\bar{x} - x_0) + \frac{\hbar G|\bar{\alpha}|^2 + \bar{F}_{ext}}{m_{eff}}}_{=0 \text{ (steady state)}} - \Omega_M^2\delta x(t) - \Gamma_M\delta\dot{x}(t) + \frac{\hbar G(\bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^* + \bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha) + F_{ext}(t)}{m_{eff}}
\end{aligned} \tag{2.34}$$

where the δ from the $\delta F_{ext}(t)$ is dropped as we are representing a perturbation. Therefore, the linearized equation of motion for the mechanical oscillator is

$$\delta\ddot{x}(t) = -\Omega_M^2\delta x(t) - \Gamma_M\delta\dot{x}(t) + \frac{\hbar G(\bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^* + \bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha) + \delta F_{ext}(t)}{m_{eff}}. \tag{2.35}$$

where this equation describes the small mechanical fluctuations driven by the fluctuating optical field and the fluctuating external force around the steady state. This external force is any additional force acting on the system other than the one for the optomechanical interaction. This can include thermal forces, intentionally applied forces [8] and other environmental components.

Similarly, for the cavity field amplitude, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta\dot{\alpha}(t) &= [i(\Delta + G(\bar{x} + \delta x(t))) - \kappa/2](\bar{\alpha} + \delta\alpha(t)) + \sqrt{\kappa_{ex}}\alpha_{in} \\
&\approx [i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2]\bar{\alpha} + [i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2]\delta\alpha(t) + iG\delta x(t)\bar{\alpha} + \sqrt{\kappa_{ex}}\alpha_{in} \\
&= \underbrace{[i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2]\bar{\alpha} + \sqrt{\kappa_{ex}}\alpha_{in}}_{=0 \text{ (steady state)}} + [i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2]\delta\alpha(t) + iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x(t).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.36}$$

So the linearized equation of motion for the cavity field amplitude is

$$\delta\dot{\alpha}(t) = [i(\Delta + G\bar{x}) - \kappa/2]\delta\alpha(t) + iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x(t). \tag{2.37}$$

The effective detuning $\Delta_{eff} = \Delta + G\bar{x}$ is often used to simplify this expression further, resulting in

$$\delta\dot{\alpha}(t) = [i(\Delta_{eff}) - \kappa/2]\delta\alpha(t) + iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x(t). \tag{2.38}$$

Hence, Eqs. (2.35) and (2.38) are the linearized equations of motion for the optomechanical system around its steady state.

2.3 | Phonon Dynamics

We can study this phenomenon simply by considering a light beam scattering off any object. This object needs to be closely studied to understand its behaviour when the light interacts with it. The term 'phonons' arises when we are considering a quanta of mechanical vibration. Phonons are bosonic quasi-particles, and describe them quantum mechanically, we use the phonon creation and annihilation operators, \hat{b}^\dagger and \hat{b} respectively. The zero-point fluctuation amplitude (x_{ZPF}) represents the size or spread of a mechanical oscillator's motion when it is in its quantum ground state, representing a fundamental quantum limit for detecting displacement [5]. This parameter sets the scale for the quantum mechanical motion of the oscillator [6], which is described using phonons.

When we have photons bouncing off a mechanical part in our system, the light will exhibit some scattering. There exists two types of scattering, namely elastic light scattering and inelastic scattering.

Elastic light scattering occurs when the frequency of the light that bounces off the object (whether it is an atom, nanobeam, particle [8]) is the same as the original incoming frequency. This can be mathematically described as $\omega = \omega'$ where ω is the original frequency and ω' is the outgoing frequency.

On the other hand, inelastic scattering involves the exchange of energy between the light and the object, whether its the excitation or de-excitation of the material. Raman scattering is a typical form of inelastic scattering in optomechanics which arises from the object's mechanical vibrations. This can be denoted as $\omega' = \omega \mp \Omega$ where the frequency of the scattered light is shifted by Ω which denotes the vibrational frequency from the phonons.

These inelastic scatterings can be described by Stokes and anti-Stokes processes. For the Stokes process, $\omega' = \omega - \Omega$ where the scattered photon has a lower frequency than the incident photon, which means that it is red-shifted. In this case the oscillator gains energy as a phonon which is a quantised mechanical vibration, known as the blue-detuned case where the laser frequency ω_L is larger than the resonance frequency of the cavity ω_{cav} , leading to amplification or heating of the system. This process can be seen in part a) in Fig. 2.1, taken from [5].

For anti-Stokes processes, $\omega' = \omega + \Omega$ where the scattered photon has a higher frequency than the incident photon, so it is blue-shifted. Here, the oscillator loses energy since a phonon is annihilated and this excess energy is transferred to a photon, boosting

Figure 2.1: Photon-phonon Scattering process in blue and red detuning taken from [5].

its frequency [5]. In this case, it is said that the laser is red-detuned where its frequency is lower than the cavity resonance frequency ($\omega_L < \omega_{cav}$), leading to optomechanical cooling. This process can be seen in part b) in Fig. 2.1

If both Stokes and anti-Stokes scattering processes take place at an equal rate, then the mechanical oscillator will, on average, gain as much energy as it loses. The overall effect is a net increase in the energy of the vibrations which results in the heating of the object or material. This is an observable and rather trivial phenomena to us considering we do not have any frequency-selective mechanisms [5].

A way to suppress the Stokes process would be to use an optical cavity. The cavity can house resonances with specific frequencies, making it possible to tune the frequency of the driving laser (the incoming light) relative to the cavity resonance (the natural resonant frequencies of the cavity) and mechanical frequency (natural oscillation frequency of the mechanical element. This can be a microbeam, movable mirror, or any kind of mechanical resonator). This is called red-tuning the laser. In this case, the cavity's density of states can be controlled to favour the blue-shifted scattered photons - the anti-Stokes frequency while making it difficult for scattering at the red-shifted Stokes frequency.

Photons are preferentially back-scattered (the light that leaves the cavity after an interaction with the optomechanical system) with a blue-shifted frequency when the Stokes process is suppressed. Each scattered photon carries away an amount of energy, $\hbar\Omega$ which corresponds to the energy lost by the mechanical oscillator when the phonon is annihilated. Eventually, this continuous energy removal from the mechanical oscillator which means the system undergoes the reduction of vibrational energy, cooling the system. This sets the foundation for cavity-assisted cooling [5]. Effectively, the thermal energy from the mechanical oscillator gets extracted by the laser. Mechanisms as such can prove to be very useful, where the Stokes and anti-Stokes processes are leveraged to get the most out of a particular system.

The optical cavity is what allows for the superposition of the Stokes process along with the optimisation of the anti-Stokes process by its resonant properties. The cavity will have different responses at different frequencies around the laser frequency (a phenomena called detuning) since the responses of the cavity are now asymmetrical [5]. Another application is when the cavity needs to allow for the sensitive monitoring of the mechanical vibrations through the transformations they create in the transmitted or reflected light.

2.4 | Cavity Optomechanics

The Fabry-Pérot setup is described as the typical system in cavity optomechanics [6]. Since the late 1960's, it has been a significant configuration. The setup includes an optical cavity having a vibrating end-mirror [5, 6]. It continues to be an important system for fundamental demonstrations in the field of cavity optomechanics.

The mechanical vibrations and the optical cavity modes couple when the mechanical motion alters the properties of the cavity, namely by distorting the boundary conditions or by changing the refractive index [6]. When systems implement a dielectric object, the optical modes propagate through it, causing radiation forces that vibrate the object, utilising this coupling mechanism [6].

A common theoretical description of the interaction between a single optical mode and a single mechanical mode, applicable to the Fabry-Pérot cavity, begins with a Hamiltonian. For a Fabry-Pérot cavity, with an oscillating mechanical part, or when a light pulse interacts with the system, effective Hamiltonians are used to describe these dynamics.

Figure 2.2: A simple Fabry-Pérot setup, consisting of a laser driving the optical cavity where the light interacts with the end mirror as a result of the radiation pressure, resulting in the mechanical oscillator vibrating taken from [6].

A typical starting point is this Hamiltonian,

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m_{eff}} + \frac{1}{2}m_{eff}\Omega_M^2\hat{x}^2 + \hbar\omega_{cav}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} + \hbar G\hat{x}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a} \quad (2.39)$$

[7] where \hat{p} is the mechanical momentum operator, m_{eff} is the effective mass of the mechanical resonator, and Ω_M is its mechanical frequency. $\hbar\omega_{cav}\hat{a}^\dagger\hat{a}$ represents the energy of the optical cavity mode, where \hat{a}^\dagger and \hat{a} are the photon creation and annihilation operators. \hat{x} is the mechanical position operator. Additional detail about the quantum description of such a system can be found in the next chapter.

For a standard Fabry-Pérot cavity with a vibrating end mirror, as seen in Fig. 2.2 (taken from [6]) and length L , we can find that $G = d\omega_{cav}/dx = \omega_{opt}/L$ where G is the optomechanical frequency shift as a function of displacement and ω_{opt} is the optical frequency for that optical mode. This intuitively highlights that smaller cavities lead to larger coupling strengths [6]. Systems like the Fabry-pérot experiment allow the direct monitoring of the mechanical oscillator, where one can evaluate the varying mechanical position of the oscillator through the phase shift of the modulated light [5].

Some phenomena arising from the interaction of light and matter include dynamical backaction, an effect where the light is said to be acting as a spring inside the cavity, causing the continual motion of the mechanical oscillator. Quantum effects and entanglement are also an effect resulting from this type of interaction where a Fabry-Pérot cavity is used to generate these nonclassical states of light as well as entanglement be-

tween light and matter [5].

The radiation pressure potential, when combined with the mechanical oscillator potential, leads to interesting non-linear phenomena like static multistability, where multiple stable mechanical equilibrium locations can exist for a given set of parameters. When external parameters such as laser detuning are systematically changed over a certain range in one direction and then changed back over the same range but in the opposite direction, the system can follow different stable branches, leading to hysteresis in the observed response, for instance, this effect is very commonly found when recording the optical transmission. While noise can potentially remove the bistability under certain conditions, this indicates experimental challenges [9].

We deduce a relationship between the slope of the radiation pressure force and the mechanical spring constant by the equation $D = D_0 - \frac{dF}{dx}$, where the radiation pressure force F which depends on the intensity of the light within the cavity, is also influenced by the displacement of the mechanical resonator. This is obtained by finding the derivative of F , written as $-dF/dx = d^2V_{rad}(x)/dx^2 = D - D_0$. This dependence leads to a modification of the effective stiffness k of the mechanical oscillator. This describes how the optical spring effect is introduced for optomechanical systems.

The cavity's resonance frequency, and therefore the the intracavity light intensity for a laser is a function of the cavity length. When the cavity length is displaced by x , the resonance condition is thus altered due to the radiation pressure force. The radiation pressure force introduces an extra, position-dependent force to the system. Moreover, the slope, dF/dx effectively modifies the overall restoring force and so, the overall spring constant of the oscillator is effected, which means the spring constant k is not a constant any longer and highly depends on the radiation pressure force.

For blue detuning (positive detuning, as explained in Eq. (2.22)), the displacement can result in a negative linear force response, i.e., $dF/dx > 0$, which acts as an additional restoring force, effectively increasing the spring constant. This can be viewed as a stiffening of the mechanical spring. Conversely, for red detuning (negative detuning), the radiation pressure force reduces the effective spring constant, leading to a softening of the oscillator [10].

At resonance, $\Delta = 0$, the effects are negligible, however, around the half-width of the optical resonance, the effects are at a maximum and are proportional to the incident

power. Half-width is a measure of the sharpness or narrowness of the cavity's ability to enhance and store light at specific frequencies. A narrower resonance, so a smaller half-width refers to a cavity with higher quality - light stays inside the cavity for a longer time [5]. The half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) is $\kappa/2$. This determines how sharply the system responds to frequency vibrations. This measure governs how pronounced frequency shifts are near the resonance frequency. When the frequency of the input laser is scanned across these resonances, the power transmitted or reflected in the cavity exhibits peaks. The shape of these peaks is typically Lorentzian.

2.5 | Optical Spring Effect

As we have seen previously, the interaction between the light field within an optical cavity and the mechanical motion of its components results to a variety of fascinating phenomena.

One such fundamental effect is the optical spring effect, where the effective mechanical resonance frequency of an optomechanical oscillator is shifted due to the presence of light. As we discussed in chapter 2, the radiation pressure force applied by the photons circulating in the cavity is dependent on the cavity length. The cavity length can then be altered when a movable mechanical component undergoes a displacement x due to this radiation pressure force acting back on the mechanical component as well as the intracavity intensity. A change in the cavity's length therefore means that the cavity's resonance frequency is also modified. This change in resonance frequency effects the amount of light that can enter and be sustained within the cavity.

However, in many realistic scenarios, we must account for the finite cavity decay rate κ , especially when the mechanical motion is not slow. The light field does not immediately react to the mechanical motion, thus leading to a retardation in the radiation pressure force. This retardation introduces a component of the force that is out of phase with the mechanical motion, leading to optomechanical damping or amplification. The in-phase component part of this is responsible for the optical spring effect. Providing a definition for the optical spring effect, we can describe the effective mechanical resonance frequency of a shifted optomechanical oscillator due to the presence of light in the optical cavity, denoted as $\delta\Omega_M$.

The linearised equations of motion, are crucial to analyse in order to understand the optical spring effect. The optical field and the mechanical displacement are dynamically

coupled in an optomechanical system. This means that the change in the mechanical position effects the cavity response frequency which as we have said, alters the intracavity field and the radiation pressure force acting on the oscillator. It is important to examine how these quantities evolve over time.

While the fundamental optomechanical interaction is non-linear, we have linearised the equations of motion for small fluctuations around the steady-state, allowing us to simplify the analysis and observe how the system responds to small perturbations, an essential step to understand the optical spring effect. The dynamical nature of the optical spring effect implies that the modification in the mechanical resonance frequency, so $\delta\Omega_M$, is not just a static offset. This shift can be frequency-dependent, especially when the mechanical oscillation frequency Ω_M is comparable or larger than the cavity decay rate κ [5].

In order to analyse these frequency-dependent responses, it makes sense to move from the time-dependent domain to the frequency domain using Fourier Transforms. The Fourier transform $A[\omega]$ of a time-dependent function $A(t)$ is defined as:

$$A[\omega] \equiv \mathcal{F}\{A(t)\} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} dt A(t)e^{-i\omega t}. \quad (2.40)$$

The linearized equations of motion for the mechanical displacement fluctuation $\delta x(t)$ and the optical field amplitude fluctuation $\delta\alpha(t)$ as derived in chapter 2, are

$$\begin{aligned} \delta\ddot{x}(t) &= -\Omega_M^2\delta x(t) - \Gamma_M\delta\dot{x}(t) + \frac{\hbar G(\bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha(t) + \bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^*(t))}{m_{eff}} + \frac{F_{ext}(t)}{m_{eff}}, \\ \delta\dot{\alpha}(t) &= [i(\Delta_{eff}) - \kappa/2]\delta\alpha(t) + iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x(t). \end{aligned}$$

Applying the Fourier transform to the linearized equations of motion yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}\{\delta\ddot{x}(t)\} &= -\omega^2\delta x[\omega] \\ \mathcal{F}\{\delta\dot{x}(t)\} &= -i\omega\delta x[\omega] \\ \mathcal{F}\{\delta\alpha(t)\} &= \delta\alpha[\omega] \\ \mathcal{F}\{\delta\alpha^*(t)\} &= \delta\alpha^*[-\omega]. \end{aligned}$$

The first two transformations similarly hold for $\delta\dot{\alpha}(t)$ and $\delta\ddot{\alpha}(t)$, respectively.

Substituting these into the linearized equations, we transform the algebraic equations in the frequency domain. Starting with the mechanical oscillator function, we obtain

$$-\omega^2\delta x[\omega] = -\Omega_M^2\delta x[\omega] + i\omega\Gamma_M\delta x[\omega] + \frac{\hbar G}{m_{eff}}(\bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha[\omega] + \bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^*[-\omega]) + \frac{\delta F_{ext}[\omega]}{m_{eff}}. \quad (2.41)$$

Solving for $\delta x[\omega]$ yields

$$\delta x[\omega](-\omega^2 + \Omega_M^2 - i\omega\Gamma_M) = \frac{\hbar G}{m_{eff}}(\bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^*[\omega] + \bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha[\omega]) + \frac{F_{ext}[\omega]}{m_{eff}}. \quad (2.42)$$

Before we continue with our calculation, it is necessary to define the response function of the cavity, denoted as the optical susceptibility

$$\chi_c(\omega) = \frac{1}{-i\omega - i(\Delta_{eff}) + \kappa/2}. \quad (2.43)$$

$\chi_c(\omega)$ denotes how an optical cavity can withhold an optical field at a given frequency. This tells us how the cavity responds to an input light field at different frequencies. This Lorentzian form [6] suggests that the cavity responds most strongly when the driving frequency is close to the cavity resonance frequency, so when $\omega_l \approx \omega_{cav}$. The function peaks at $\Delta = 0$, when the driving laser is on resonance. This implies that the intracavity field reaches its maximum amplitude at resonance. Therefore, the magnitude of the optical susceptibility would be

$$|\chi_c(\omega)| = \left| \frac{1}{\kappa/2 - i\omega} \right|. \quad (2.44)$$

The width of this resonance is determined by the cavity decay rate κ where a smaller κ leads to a sharper resonance i.e., the cavity has a higher Q-factor. This proves that the cavity strongly enhances and stores light at frequencies close to its resonance for a longer time period [5].

Similarly, the mechanical susceptibility governing a displacement under an external force at a frequency is

$$\chi_m(\omega) = \frac{1}{m(\Omega_m^2 - \omega^2 - i\omega\Gamma_m)}. \quad (2.45)$$

In essence, both the optical and mechanical susceptibility describe the linear response of the two fundamental components in an optomechanical system, interconnected by the optomechanical interaction. The mechanical susceptibility in the presence of optomechanical coupling is represented by

$$\chi_{xx}(\omega) = \chi_m(\omega) + \Sigma(\omega)^{-1} \quad (2.46)$$

where $\Sigma(\omega)$ represents the optomechanical interaction terms combined, often called the optomechanical self-energy. We continue by transforming for the optical field, giving

$$-i\omega\delta\alpha[\omega] = [i(\Delta_{eff}) - \kappa/2]\delta\alpha[\omega] + iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x[\omega]. \quad (2.47)$$

Solving for $\delta\alpha[\omega]$,

$$\delta\alpha[\omega] = \frac{iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x[\omega]}{(\kappa/2 - i\omega - i\Delta_{eff})} \quad (2.48)$$

We can substitute the optical susceptibility

$$\delta\alpha[\omega] = \chi_c(\omega) (iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x[\omega]) \quad (2.49)$$

The term $(\bar{\alpha}\delta\alpha^*[\omega] + \bar{\alpha}^*\delta\alpha[\omega])$ in Eq. (2.42) can now be solved in terms of the optical susceptibility using the property $(\delta x[-\omega])^* = \delta x[\omega]$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Since } (\delta\bar{\alpha}^*)[\omega] &= (\delta\alpha[-\omega])^*, \\ \delta\alpha^*[\omega] &= (\chi_c[-\omega]iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x[-\omega])^* \\ \delta\alpha^*[\omega] &= -iG\bar{\alpha}^*\chi_c^*[-\omega]\delta x[\omega] \end{aligned} \quad (2.50)$$

where $\delta x(t)$ is real-valued, allowing us to make these calculations.

These solutions can be substituted back into Eq. (2.42), giving us

$$\begin{aligned} \delta x[\omega](-\omega^2 + \Omega_M^2 - i\omega\Gamma_M) &= \frac{\hbar G}{m_{eff}} (-iG\bar{\alpha}^*\chi_c^*[-\omega]\delta x[\omega] + \bar{\alpha}^*iG\bar{\alpha}\delta x[\omega]\chi_c[\omega]) + \frac{F_{ext}[\omega]}{m_{eff}} \\ \delta x[\omega] \left(\Omega_M^2 - \omega^2 - i\omega\Gamma_M - \frac{i\hbar G|\bar{\alpha}|^2}{m_{eff}}(\chi_c[\omega] - \chi_c^*[-\omega]) \right) &= \frac{F_{ext}[\omega]}{m_{eff}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.51)$$

Here, we can combine the terms that depend on the interaction, so G , and obtain the optomechanical self-energy

$$\Sigma(\omega) = -\frac{i\hbar G|\bar{\alpha}|^2}{m_{eff}}(\chi_c[\omega] - \chi_c^*[-\omega]). \quad (2.52)$$

Therefore, the equation for the mechanical response becomes

$$\delta x[\omega] = \frac{F_{ext}(\omega)}{m_{eff}(\Omega_M^2 - \omega^2 - i\omega\Gamma_M + \Sigma(\omega))}. \quad (2.53)$$

The prefactor appearing in the optomechanical self-energy can be rewritten in a more insightful form as

$$G^2|\bar{\alpha}|^2 = 2m_{eff}\Omega_M g^2, \quad (2.54)$$

where the optical frequency shift per unit displacement (i.e., the optomechanical coupling strength in units of Hz/m), and $\bar{\alpha}$ is the steady-state amplitude of the intracavity field and both can be written in terms of Ω_M .

To arrive at this expression, we use the definition of the zero-point fluctuation amplitude,

$$x_{\text{ZPF}} = \left(\frac{\hbar}{2m_{\text{eff}}\Omega_M} \right)^{1/2},$$

which characterizes the quantum uncertainty in the mechanical position at zero temperature. The single-photon optomechanical coupling strength g is defined by the relation $g = Gx_{\text{ZPF}}$. Therefore, we can write

$$(Gx_{\text{ZPF}}|\bar{a}|)^2 = g^2|\bar{a}|^2, \quad (2.55)$$

and thus recover the result in Eq. (2.54).

In the weak-coupling regime, where the optomechanical interaction does not significantly cross optical and mechanical modes, the mechanical response still exhibits a single, well-defined resonance. However, the position and width of this resonance are modified by the optical field. A closer look at the denominator of the mechanical response in Eq. (2.53), reveals that the real part of Σ shifts the mechanical resonance frequency [6] — a consequence of the optical spring effect. However, the imaginary part of Σ leads to optomechanically induced damping, depending on the laser detuning.

Mathematically, these are written as

$$\Gamma_{\text{opt}} = -\frac{1}{m_{\text{eff}}\Omega_M} \text{Im} \Sigma(\Omega) \quad (2.56)$$

$$= g^2\kappa \left\{ \frac{1}{(\Omega_M + \bar{\Delta})^2 + \left(\frac{\kappa}{2}\right)^2} - \frac{1}{(\Omega_M - \bar{\Delta})^2 + \left(\frac{\kappa}{2}\right)^2} \right\} \quad (2.57)$$

where the imaginary component accounts for the light-induced modification of the optomechanical damping rate. This expression can be positive (leading to damping and cooling) or negative (leading to anti-damping and amplification), again depending on the detuning Δ .

Meanwhile, the real part of the expression represents the shift of the mechanical frequency as discussed. This is the optical spring effect, denoted as

$$\delta(\Omega^2) = \frac{1}{m_{\text{eff}}} \text{Re} \Sigma(\Omega) \quad (2.58)$$

$$= 2\Omega_M g^2 \left\{ \frac{\Omega_M + \bar{\Delta}}{(\Omega_M + \bar{\Delta})^2 + \left(\frac{\kappa}{2}\right)^2} - \frac{\Omega_M - \bar{\Delta}}{(\Omega_M - \bar{\Delta})^2 + \left(\frac{\kappa}{2}\right)^2} \right\}. \quad (2.59)$$

Both imaginary and real results are consequences of dynamical backaction [6]. Plotting these key effects of the optomechanical interaction - the dynamical back action gives us Fig. 2.3 and Fig. 2.4 inspired from [6]. The different red lines within each figure represent different values of the ratio κ/Ω_M , the optical cavity decay rate relative to the mechanical resonance frequency and their behaviour.

Fig. 2.3 represents the mechanical damping rate as a function of the effective detuning and how it is modified by the light field, hence it being named Optomechanical damping. Γ_{opt} in the vertical axis represents this change in the mechanical damping rate. The positive values of Γ_{opt} exhibit additional damping or cooling, while the negative values of Γ_{opt} represent amplification or heating. In the resolved sideband regime, where the mechanical resonance frequency is much larger than the optical cavity decay rate $\kappa < \Omega_m$, the anti-stokes processes or the stokes processes can be selectively enhanced since we have ideal conditions for lasing in this regime. The damping rate is shown rescaled, representing the parametric dependence of Γ_{opt} in the resolved-sideband regime. In essence, the optomechanical damping rate fundamentally depends on the square of the enhanced coupling strength g (which depends on the laser power) divided by the cavity decay rate κ .

Meanwhile for Fig. 2.4, we can observe the Optical spring effect in the form of the mechanical frequency shifts as a function of the effective detuning. The figure displays the frequency shift in terms of $\delta(\Omega^2) \approx 2\Omega_M\delta\Omega$ for small $\delta\Omega \ll \Omega_M$. The detuning strongly effects this frequency shift, for red detuning $\bar{\Delta} < 0$, the mechanical frequency is increased, so the curve is at its highest here. For blue detuning $\bar{\Delta} > 0$, the frequency is decreased. On the other hand, for a blue-detuned laser, the optical spring effect usually causes a stiffening of the mechanical oscillator, leading to an increase in its resonance frequency. The frequency shift can exhibit more complicated dispersive behaviour when the mechanical frequency is comparable to or larger than the cavity decay rate κ .

A parameter that plays a crucial part in the outcome of this system and the interactions is of course the optomechanical coupling strength g . The vacuum optomechanical coupling strength g_0 , which characterizes the fundamental interaction between a single photon and a single phonon, also influences the magnitude of the optical spring effect. Naturally, a larger g_0 leads to a stronger coupling and a greater frequency shift for a given intracavity power.

Another key parameter is the cavity linewidth. So far, we have referenced this param-

Figure 2.3: A plot of the scaled optomechanical damping rate as a function of the detuning. Positive peaks denote stronger damping, meanwhile negative peaks indicate an anti-damping.

eter as κ , the cavity decay rate, which is related to the cavity's finesse and photon lifetime, affects the frequency dependence and the magnitude of the optical spring effect. The relationship between the frequency shift and the detuning is influenced by the cavity linewidth, particularly when the mechanical frequency Ω_M is not much smaller than κ . The optical spring effect directly influences the mechanical resonance frequency. The effective mechanical resonance frequency $\Omega_{m_{eff}}$ is shifted from the intrinsic mechanical resonance frequency by the optical spring effect, such that $\Omega_{M_{eff}} = \Omega_M + \delta\Omega_M$ [6]. This light-induced tunability of the mechanical resonance frequency offers various applications, including sensing and the control of mechanical oscillators [6].

However, the optical spring effect has limitations. The magnitude of the frequency shift is restricted by the stability of the optomechanical system, particularly in the blue-

Figure 2.4: Frequency shift based on the optomechanical interaction as a function of the detuning.

detuned regime where strong amplification can lead to mechanical instabilities (self-induced oscillations or mechanical lasing) when the effective damping rate becomes negative which is required for phonon lasing.

Phonon lasing will be a key topic further on in this research, these are the self-induced mechanical oscillations as previously mentioned. The optical spring effect plays a crucial role by shifting the mechanical resonance frequency, which can affect the conditions for the onset (the starting point for the self-induced oscillations as the system's conditions are met) and the frequency of the oscillations. Understanding the light-induced frequency shift is therefore essential for manipulating phonon lasing in cavity optomechanical systems.

The optical spring effect has been experimentally observed in many optomechanical systems. Early exploration and analysis of optomechanical effects on the damping rate

and effective spring constant were done by Braginsky and co-workers in macroscopic microwave setups in the late 1960s [5]. Some more recent experiments have shown the optical spring effect in nanomechanical oscillators coupled to high-finesse optical microresonators via their evanescent field [11]. Such experiments have even shown laser-like coherent nanomechanical oscillations just by radiation pressure, highlighting the impact of dynamical backaction and the optical spring effect in such systems [11]. The optical spring effect has also been demonstrated in measurements of optomechanical frequency shifts in systems with cold atoms trapped in optical cavities [5].

Optical Spring Effect in Multimode Optomechanical system

Source [12] considers the case of two mechanical modes, where it was found a laser drive that is modulated at the difference between two mechanical frequencies can induce mode-locked coherent oscillations of both modes. We expand the same analysis for three mechanical modes as denoted in Eq. (3.3), with a schematic displaying this system in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 3.1: A schematic of three mechanical modes coupled to one optical mode.

However, we know that the optical spring effect can cause the frequencies of the individual mechanical modes for a two-moded system (Ω_1 and Ω_2) to shift [12]. If these shifts are different for the three modes, it will lead to a change in their frequency difference.

If the frequency difference between these three mechanical modes differs greatly from the modulation frequency, due to this spring effect, then the conditions for multimode mechanical lasing will be disrupted, destabilizing the mode-locked state. If this frequency change is within the range of the mechanical linewidth, then we obtain lasing.

However, if the frequency difference overrides the mechanical linewidth, then our system would not produce coherent oscillations.

Our goal is to examine the change in frequency between the mechanical modes since mode-locking implies a balanced relationship between the phases and frequencies of the oscillating modes.

The shift in the mechanical frequency is written as

$$\delta(\Omega_M^2) = \frac{1}{m_{eff}} \text{Re}\Sigma(\Omega_M) \quad (3.1)$$

where in [6] it is defined as

$$\delta(\Omega_M^2) = 2\Omega_M g_M^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_M + \bar{\Delta}}{(\Omega_M + \bar{\Delta})^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{\Omega_M - \bar{\Delta}}{(\Omega_M - \bar{\Delta})^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right). \quad (3.2)$$

Here, we will take the simplest case assume that we have three equidistantly spaced mechanical modes

$$\Omega_1 + \bar{\delta} = \Omega_2 = \Omega_3 - \bar{\delta} \quad (3.3)$$

where we are taking our reference point around Ω_2 . For this case, we will also take effective laser detuning $\bar{\Delta}$ to be equal to the frequency of the central mechanical mode Ω_2 . This allows us to study phenomena that occur when the laser is tuned to be resonant with a sideband of the mechanical mode.

The new frequencies of each mode can be expressed as

$$\Omega'_M = \sqrt{\Omega_M^2 + \delta(\Omega_M^2)}. \quad (3.4)$$

In order to obtain mode-locked multimode lasing between these three mechanical modes, we will assume ideal conditions, $\Delta + G\bar{x} = \Omega_2$ where the effective laser detuning (the initial detuning Δ plus the shift due to steady-state mechanical displacement $G\bar{x}$) is equal to the resonance frequency of the second and central mode.

This implies that setting the effective detuning to be resonant with one of the mechanical mode frequencies is an ideal condition for driving the system towards multimode lasing when the laser is modulated at the frequency difference δ between the mechanical modes.

Other ideal conditions include $\Delta = \omega_{op} - \omega_L$ which represents the bare detuning of the central laser frequency from the resonance frequency of the optical cavity and the frequency at which the driving laser is modulated Ω_{mod} is equal to the frequency difference δ between the mechanical modes. The latter condition allows for efficient energy exchange and phase locking between modes [12].

We now express the frequency shifts for each mode using Eq. (3.2) where

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_1)^2} = \sqrt{2\Omega_1 g_1^2 \left\{ \frac{\Omega_1 + \Omega_2}{(\Omega_1 + \Omega_2)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{\Omega_1 - \Omega_2}{(\Omega_1 - \Omega_2)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}, \quad (3.5)$$

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_2)^2} = \sqrt{2\Omega_2 g_2^2 \left\{ \frac{2\Omega_2}{(2\Omega_2)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}, \quad (3.6)$$

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_3)^2} = \sqrt{2\Omega_3 g_3^2 \left\{ \frac{\Omega_3 + \Omega_2}{(\Omega_3 + \Omega_2)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{\Omega_3 - \Omega_2}{(\Omega_3 - \Omega_2)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}. \quad (3.7)$$

Since we are taking Ω_2 to be our central mode, we will now take the modes Ω_1 and Ω_3 in terms of Ω_2 using Eq. (3.3).

Because the modes are equally spaced and we are assuming ideal conditions, we also have $g_1 = g_2 = g_3$, $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma_2 = \Gamma_3$ and $\kappa_1 = \kappa_2 = \kappa_3$. Rewriting, we get

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_1)^2} = \sqrt{2(\Omega_2 - \delta)g^2 \left\{ \frac{2\Omega_2 - \delta}{(2\Omega_2 - \delta)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{(-\delta)}{(-\delta)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_3)^2} = \sqrt{2(\Omega_2 + \delta)g^2 \left\{ \frac{2\Omega_2 + \delta}{(2\Omega_2 + \delta)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{\delta}{\delta^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}. \quad (3.9)$$

These frequency shifts are now substituted in Eq. (3.4) for each mode,

$$\Omega'_1 = \sqrt{\Omega_1^2 + 2(\Omega_2 - \delta)g^2 \left\{ \frac{2\Omega_2 - \delta}{(2\Omega_2 - \delta)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{(-\delta)}{(-\delta)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}, \quad (3.10)$$

$$\Omega'_2 = \sqrt{2\Omega_2 g^2 \left\{ \frac{2\Omega_2}{(2\Omega_2)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}, \quad (3.11)$$

$$\Omega'_3 = \sqrt{\Omega_3^2 + 2(\Omega_2 + \delta)g^2 \left\{ \frac{2\Omega_2 + \delta}{(2\Omega_2 + \delta)^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} - \frac{\delta}{\delta^2 + (\kappa/2)^2} \right\}}. \quad (3.12)$$

where here we have the new frequencies for each mode.

The frequency difference between the three mechanical modes should match the modulation frequency on the same order of the mechanical linewidth $\Gamma/2$ to maximise the contribution from the Floquet process - the process which allows for the achievement of multimode lasing with mode locking using a time-periodic modulation in the optical drive to exhibit specific interactions between mechanical modes in the system [12].

When this condition $|\Omega_l - \Omega_j| \approx \Omega_{mod}$, arising from the Floquet process, is met, the modulation practically closes the frequency gap between the mechanical modes. This allows processes like stimulated emission of a cavity photon and a phonon, generating a coherent phonon in a different mode, which can seed mode locking [12].

This modulation creates sidebands - new frequency components that can be strategically used to interact with many mechanical modes, allowing for the processes as discussed. This condition is described as $\omega_L \pm n\Omega_{mod}$ where n is the n th mode.

3.1 | Results

We take the experimental values for the simplest case from [12] as written in table 3.1.

Parameter	Value in Hz
Ω_1	$2\pi \times 3.845 \times 10^9$
Ω_2	$2\pi \times 3.899 \times 10^9$
Ω_3	$2\pi \times 3.955 \times 10^9$
Ω_{mod}	$2\pi \times 54 \times 10^6$
$\Gamma_1 = \Gamma_2 = \Gamma_3$	$2\pi \times 2.7 \times 10^6$
$g_1 = g_2 = g_3$	$2\pi \times 687 \times 10^3$
$\kappa_1 = \kappa_2 = \kappa_3$	$2\pi \times 14.88 \times 10^9$

Table 3.1: Experimental values.

These values can now be substituted into Eqs. (3.10) to (3.12).

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\delta(\Omega_1)^2} &= 3.124323761 \times 10^6 \text{Hz} \\ \Omega'_1 &= 2.415884771 \times 10^{10} \text{Hz} \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\delta(\Omega_2)^2} &= 3.12310415 \times 10^6 \text{Hz} \\ \Omega'_2 &= 2.449813971 \times 10^{10} \text{Hz} \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\delta(\Omega_3)^2} &= 3.121178311 \times 10^6 \text{Hz} \\ \Omega'_3 &= 2.484999809 \times 10^{10} \text{Hz} \end{aligned} \quad (3.15)$$

Analysing $(\Omega'_2 - \Omega'_1) - (\Omega_2 - \Omega_1)$ determines how much the optical spring effect alters the original frequency difference between mechanical modes Ω_1 and Ω_2 . Therefore,

$$(\Omega'_2 - \Omega'_1) - (\Omega_2 - \Omega_1) = -2.57456 \times 10^4 \text{Hz} \quad (3.16)$$

Similarly, we find the difference for Ω_3 ,

$$(\Omega'_3 - \Omega'_2) - (\Omega_3 - \Omega_2) = 2.7979\text{Hz} \quad (3.17)$$

Comparing the difference of the frequency shifts with the mechanical linewidth Γ ,

$$|(\Omega'_2 - \Omega'_1) - (\Omega_2 - \Omega_1)| = 2.57456 \times 10^4 \text{Hz} < \Gamma \quad (3.18)$$

Similarly,

$$2.7979\text{Hz} < \Gamma \quad (3.19)$$

3.2 | Discussion

Achieving self-sustained coherent oscillations is a challenging task as there are limiting effects that prevent or interfere with obtaining the stable lasing. As mentioned, these effects include gain competition, where one mode is gravitated to override other modes. In our analytical analysis, we used a modulated laser. This modulation was applied at a frequency that is around the same value as the frequency differences between the mechanical modes. By matching these frequencies in the same order as the mechanical linewidth, we can compare them directly, since the mechanical linewidth sets the fundamental spectral range within which Floquet-induced coupling and energy exchange need to occur effectively for phase locking, meaning that our system would now generate stable, multi-mode coherent oscillations.

The dynamical backaction of the light field on the mechanical resonator results in the optical spring effect which alters the effective stiffness of the mechanical part, shifting the resonance frequency of the mechanical mode. In a multimode system, one would intuitively imagine that the optical spring effect would shift the bare frequency of the mechanical modes $(\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \Omega_3)$ independently, breaking their equal spacing, into new effective frequencies $(\Omega'_1, \Omega'_2, \Omega'_3)$. The important question for analysing the optical spring's limitation in the multimode lasing state is how these shifts affect the relative frequency differences between the mechanical modes that we are targeting.

Using existing parameters from [12], our calculation focused on a system containing three mechanical modes. These parameters included the bare mechanical frequencies $(\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \Omega_3)$ which were initially assumed to be equally spaced, a specific modulation frequency (Ω_{mod}) , mechanical linewidths (Γ) , optomechanical coupling rates (g) and optical cavity decay rates (κ) . Although we started with equally spaced modes and

equal coupling rates ($g_1 = g_2 = g_3$) and linewidths ($\Gamma_1 = \Gamma_2 = \Gamma_3$) were assumed, the calculated optical-induced shifts for each mode were slightly different,

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_1)^2} = 3.124323761 \times 10^6 \text{Hz}, \quad (3.20)$$

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_2)^2} = 3.12310415 \times 10^6 \text{Hz}, \quad (3.21)$$

$$\sqrt{\delta(\Omega_3)^2} = 3.121178311 \times 10^6 \text{Hz}. \quad (3.22)$$

$$(3.23)$$

These differential shifts indicate how the effective frequencies are not precisely equally spaced, even if the bare frequencies were due to the optical spring effect. However, the critical factor for the strength of the mode-locked state is whether the induced change in the difference between the mechanical mode frequencies is enough to impact our system when compared to the original spacing and the linewidth. Although we still detected some shift from the optical spring effect, it is effectively negligible when compared to the linewidth.

Plotting this negligible frequency shift just for Ω_1 gives us Fig. 3.2 where we can observe the scaled frequency shift as a function of detuning with a very large κ , which is the case for our results, and a smaller κ . The smaller the κ , the more of the curve in the frequency shift we see which supports the fact that even though we are operating in the unresolved regime, we get a negligible frequency shift from the optical spring effect and can possibly achieve lasing.

Figure 3.2: The frequency shift for one Ω_M with different κ values in the resolved sideband regime $\kappa/\Omega_M < 1$ (solid line) and in the unresolved sideband regime $\kappa/\Omega_M > 1$ (dashed line).

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research has explored key aspects of multimode phonon lasing in optomechanical systems, building on the principles of radiation pressure-induced self-oscillations in the field of cavity optomechanics.

The focus was mainly on the multimode scenario, enabled via temporally modulated laser drives, a technique aimed at overcoming gain competition that typically limits lasing to a single mechanical mode, and achieving mode-locked mechanical modes. Achieving coherent oscillations of multiple mechanical modes simultaneously is significant for potential applications of multimode systems.

Our analysis focused on a system with three mechanical modes in the unresolved regime. This system highlighted the interplay between modulated optical drive and the dynamics of the system and the dependence of each in obtaining a lasing state. The analytical analysis demonstrated how phonon lasing was achieved through the modulated optical drive even in the unresolved regime.

A central theme of this work has been the investigation of the optical spring effect on the stability of this multimode lasing state. We have explored how the optical spring, which is a result of dynamical backaction, shifts the effective frequencies of the mechanical modes- this was the core idea of the interaction of radiation pressure force with the mechanical part of a system. Our findings indicate that while the optical spring effect is present, its impact on the frequency difference between the oscillating mechanical modes was small, small enough to stay within the lasing ranges dictated by the linewidth, and we obtained the analytical results for stable, coherent multimode phonon lasing.

Overall, this work contributes to the understanding of multimode phonon lasing by demonstrating the conditions required for stable mode locking in a three-mode system under modulated driving, maintaining control over the optical spring effect to prevent it from disrupting our conditions. These findings can have many functionalities in the

field of cavity optomechanics, namely in areas such as highly stable ultracompact oscillators [12] and timekeeping devices [12]. Beyond these direct applications of the coherent oscillations, the advancements in multimode mode-locked operation open up a broader range of applications such as serving as building blocks for more complex optomechanical circuits capable of sensing, amplification and general signal processing [5] as well as functioning as tunable optical filters or laser stabilisation [5] and highly sensitive detection applications for small forces, displacements, masses and accelerations [5].

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